

The Impact of Burnout and Compensation on Turnover Intention Mediated by Job Satisfaction in a Private Hospital in Tangerang

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to find that burnout and compensation have a significant effect on job satisfaction and turnover intention, and job satisfaction can function as a mediator between burnout, compensation, and turnover intention in health workers and health support staff at One of the Private Hospitals in Tangerang. This study uses a descriptive quantitative approach with a cross-sectional study design. The accessible population in this study were health workers and health support staff from January to May 2024 with a total accessible population of 1,030 health workers and health support staff. This study uses a non-probability purposive sample, the selected subjects meet the inclusion and exclusion requirements, so that based on the formula and requirements, 288 samples were obtained. The data analysis technique uses path analysis with testing and data analysis in this study assisted by using SMART PLS 3.0 software. The results of the analysis show that burnout has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. and a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, and a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. In addition, burnout negatively and significantly affects turnover intention through the mediation of job satisfaction, while compensation also negatively and significantly affects turnover intention through the mediation of job satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Burnout, Compensation, Job Satisfaction, Turnover Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Everyone who works for a company or organization is called human resources (HR). In hospital services, HR is involved in health service activities and can be used for health worker education in research, which includes outpatient services, inpatient services, emergency services, home care. Private Hospitals in the Tangerang area experienced a turnover of health workers during 2021–2023, with fluctuations of 8.3% in 2021, 10.9% in 2022, and 6.7% in 2023. Medical support staff increased in 2021 by 4.5%, 2022 by 5.3%, and 2023 by 5.6%. The number of employees who left during 3 years was 227 employees. Hospitals can experience losses if there is high turnover because they spend money to recruit new employees, including providing special training to get the right talent.

Table 1. Employee Turnover Data of a Private Hospital in Tangerang Area

Throughput Description	Work unit	Throughput Turnover		
		2021	2022	2023
Employees at the beginning of the year	Health Workers (A)	633	682	655
	Health support personnel (B)	352	361	359
Employee comes in	Health workers	91	55	54
	Health support staff	27	24	18
Employee out	Health workers	55	73	44
	Health support staff	16	19	20
End of year employees	Health workers	687	658	667
	Health support staff	359	359	354
Turnover percentage	Health workers	8.3%	10.9%	6.7%
	Health support staff	4.5%	5.3%	5.6%
	Total Turnover	6.9%	8.9%	6.3%

Source: Internal Hospital Data

The turnover rate of private hospitals in the Tangerang area in 2021-2023 is still in an ideal condition. Although it is ideal, employee turnover cannot be underestimated because it can have a negative impact on the hospital. One of the private hospitals in the Tangerang area stipulates that monthly turnover should not exceed 12%. However, Naranjo et al. (2016) stated that the ideal turnover standard for installations or companies is 5-10% per year.

Table 2. Data on Reasons for Employees Leaving

Year	Reason for Exit throughput				
	Exit APS	Contract ends	Pure Pension	Early retirement	Die
2021	66	3	1	0	1
2022	76	8	8	0	0
2023	58	4	1	0	1

Source: Internal Hospital Data

The most common reasons for employees to leave one of the private hospitals in the Tangerang area are using APS (at their own request), followed by reasons such as expired contracts, early retirement, and death. Reasons for their own request such as work not in accordance with the initial work contract, wanting to establish or develop their own business, family reasons, health problems, unhealthy work environment, fatigue, dissatisfaction, inappropriate compensation and for health workers such as general practitioners may continue to specialist school. Employees often face various situations or circumstances that can cause problems, such as tasks given to an employee that must be completed within a certain time. According to Mahendrawan (2015), too much physical and mental responsibility can make work difficult. This can affect or trigger stress at work and job dissatisfaction, so that it can increase the desire to leave work.

Job satisfaction is an important factor for employees of an organization because it can influence the desire to leave workers. Job satisfaction can be defined as how well a person feels about the work they do. Job satisfaction comes from compensation, human resources, job clarity, and career advancement that employees experience when they work at their workplace and feel that their work is worthy of them. Job dissatisfaction can lead to lower turnover (Alam & Asim, 2019). The desire to do something is called desire, while turnover intention is when someone voluntarily leaves their job. This will have a negative impact on the business in terms of performance and costs (Halimah et al., 2016).

There is a correlation between the desire to leave the job and satisfaction or workload. Companies can fire an employee for incompetence if they leave the company voluntarily or due to involuntary turnover. According to Zaki & Marzolina (2016) Another study on Bank Jateng employees found that job satisfaction and job stress influenced the desire to leave. Job satisfaction has a negative effect on turnover intention, but job stress has a positive effect (Widjanarko et al., 2022). In addition, research by Zakaria et al. (2017) showed that compensation has a negative effect on the desire to leave the job, with work ties as a mediating factor. In this study, job satisfaction often functions as a mediating variable between compensation or workload and turnover intention. These findings, however, may differ depending on the context and population studied.

The purpose of this study found that burnout and compensation have a significant effect on job satisfaction and turnover intention, and job satisfaction can function as a mediator between burnout, compensation, and turnover intention. If employees feel that they receive appropriate compensation, they will be more likely to improve their performance and reduce their desire to leave their company. If customers are satisfied with the goods and services offered, they are more likely to buy the same goods and services again or return. Hospitals that can meet customer needs can increase profits and markets because customer arrivals and checks increase and decreased turnover intention in employees will help reduce the company's operational burden on recruiting new employees. If employees are given attractive salaries, incentives, and provide clear opportunities to grow in their careers, this can help reduce burnout and improve their performance, thereby reducing the desire to move. This can be achieved by reducing stress levels in the workplace, creating a positive work environment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Turnover Intention

If an employee discovers that his working circumstances no longer meet his expectations, turnover is typically one of his last alternatives (Halimsetiono, 2014). The propensity or intensity of people leaving a company for a variety of reasons, such as the desire to get a higher position, is another way to define turnover (Iskandar et al., 2021). Astiti et al. (2020) define turnover intention as an employee's deliberate decision to quit the organization for a specific cause. In order to reduce employee turnover, companies must investigate the causes of employee turnover in more detail. The percentage of employee turnover in a company can be calculated using the turnover rate index, which is calculated as a percentage over a certain period of time, usually one year (Hasibuan, 2012:64; Iskandar et al., 2021).

Burnout

Burnout is a condition caused by long-term exposure to work and mental stress of clients accompanied by physical, emotional, and mental symptoms (Nodoushan et al., 2022). According to Afrianty & Dewi (2022), high-intensity workloads that do not match an employee's abilities and skills can cause employee burnout. Burnout is a syndrome involving feelings of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and feelings of low personal accomplishment, leading to decreased effectiveness in the workplace. There are five indicators of burnout, namely Maslach's depersonalization or lack of self-esteem, physical or physical exhaustion, emotional or emotional exhaustion, and mental or mental exhaustion (Hidayatullah, 2016). Three symptoms of burnout can be found, according to (Maslach et al., 2016). The first is Physical exhaustion: a person feels tired quickly while working, second Emotional exhaustion: a decrease in feelings or mentality due to work causes a person to feel tired at work; and the last is Decrease in profitability: decreased work performance can be an indication that someone is experiencing work fatigue at work.

Compensation

With increasing competition, every company must have the ability to improve and empower its resources. One of the most crucial feedbacks for both businesses and people is compensation. Employee performance may be improved and organizational goals can eventually be met by basing it on individual, group, or business performance. One of the most important components in improving employee performance is compensation (Wandi, 2022). All types of compensation that apply to employees because of their work are considered compensation. One way to motivate and optimize high-quality human resources is compensation. This is also a strategic development path (Suaedah, 2020). Compensation can also be used as a way for companies to thank their employees for their time, energy, and thoughts for the company (Purnawati, 2019). Then, for employees as individuals, compensation that is tangible financially becomes important because this amount is often considered to be able to show how important their work is to society, their families, and themselves. This compensation shows the status, recognition, and level of fulfillment of employee needs. In general, the purpose of the compensation program is for the benefit of the company, employees, government, and society. Compensation programs must be created based on fair and reasonable principles, labor laws, and internal and external consistency so that this goal is achieved and provides satisfaction for all parties (Arifudin, 2019).

Job Satisfaction

As to Badriyah (2015), job satisfaction is defined as an employee's sentiments or perspectives about positive or negative aspects of their employment that align with the opinions of their coworkers. A favorable opinion or assessment of one's own work is what Robbins et al. (2018) define as job satisfaction. Job satisfaction, broadly speaking, is the degree to which a person is content with their work and workplace. Managers must prioritize a supportive atmosphere by listening to staff issues and objectives, taking action, or encouraging team building in order to boost health workers' motivation and job satisfaction (Bonenberger et al., 2014). According to Badriyah (2015:241), a number of elements, including pay, advancement, supervision, extra perks, awards, work policies and procedures, coworkers, the task itself, and communication, affect job satisfaction.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is as follows, based on the review that was received.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Author, 2024

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a descriptive quantitative approach with a cross-sectional study design. The objects of this study are health workers and health support personnel of private hospitals in the Tangerang area. This study was conducted in July - August 2024 on health workers and health support staff at a private hospital in the Tangerang area. Using Google Forms, the research instrument delivered an electronic research questionnaire to health workers and health support staff on WhatsApp at a private hospital in the Tangerang region. One private hospital in the Tangerang region employed all of the study's target participants. The accessible population in this study were health workers and health support staff January - May 2024 with an accessible population of 1,030 health workers and health support workers. The sample to be used is a sample working in one of the private hospitals in the Tangerang area that meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The population is too large when sampling directly from each member. The sample size formula, calculated by the Slovin formula, was used in this study. With 1,030 employees in a private hospital in Tangerang, the error tolerance is 5% (0.05). This study uses a non-probability purposive sample, the selected subjects meet the inclusion and exclusion requirements, so that based on the formula and requirements, 288 samples were obtained. In order to collect initial information. The Purposive Sampling Technique method was used to distribute a total of 288 questionnaires. Data will be collected through the attached Google form with informed consent and distributed to respondents according to the number of samples required. Sent on July 20, 2024 and last received on August 20, 2024, then used for subsequent analysis. A questionnaire employing a Likert scale is used to gauge the attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions of a person or group of individuals. The SMART PLS 3.0 program helps with the data analysis approach, which employs path analysis with testing and data analysis in this investigation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of Measurement Model and Structural Model

Both the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model) are evaluated in the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach. While the inner model is assessed using the significance t test and determination coefficient test, the outer model is assessed using validity and reliability proof.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Validity is demonstrated using convergent and discriminant validity. If an indicator's filling factor value is higher than 0.50, it is deemed valid according to convergent validity (Ghozali, 2014).

Table 3. Initial Outer Loading

Variables	Indicator	Loading factor	Information
Burnout	X1	0,704	Valid
	X2	0,679	Valid
	X3	0,699	Valid
	X4	0,747	Valid
	X5	0,724	Valid
	X6	0,702	Valid
	X7	0,771	Valid
	X8	0,713	Valid
	X9	0,785	Valid
	X10	0,718	Valid
	X11	0,770	Valid
Compensation	X2.1	0,818	Valid
	X2.2	0,779	Valid
	X2.3	0,732	Valid
	X2.4	0,764	Valid
	X2.5	0,779	Valid
	X2.6	0,841	Valid
	X2.7	0,824	Valid
	X2.8	0,711	Valid
Turnover Intention	Y1	0,840	Valid
	Y2	0,796	Valid
	Y3	0,850	Valid
	Y4	0,829	Valid
	Y5	0,847	Valid
	Y6	0,774	Valid
	Y7	0,811	Valid
Job Satisfaction	Z1	0,749	Valid
	Z2	0,805	Valid
	Z3	0,748	Valid
	Z4	0,786	Valid
	Z5	0,821	Valid
	Z6	0,825	Valid
	Z7	0,767	Valid
	Z8	0,823	Valid
	Z9	0,774	Valid
	Z10	0,804	Valid
	Z11	0,785	Valid
	Z12	0,685	Valid

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The results of the analysis show that all indicators in the Burnout, Compensation, Turnover Intention, and Job Satisfaction variables have loading factors that meet the validity criteria (≥ 0.679), which indicates that each indicator is able to represent its variable well. In the Burnout variable, the indicator with the highest loading factor is X9 (0.785), while the lowest is X2 (0.679). The Compensation variable has an indicator with the highest loading factor value at X2.6 (0.841), while the lowest is X2.8 (0.711). Turnover Intention

shows high consistency with loading factor values ranging from 0.774 to 0.850, while Job Satisfaction shows a good indicator contribution even though Z12 has the lowest loading factor (0.685). All indicators are valid for use in the study model, according to these findings overall. The validity of all study variables may also be demonstrated using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, since it exceeds the 0.50 threshold (Ghozali, 2014; Fornell, 1981).

Table 4. AVE Test Results

Variables	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Burnout	0.531
Compensation	0.611
Turnover Intention	0.674
Job satisfaction	0.611

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

All four variables' Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are larger than 0.5, indicating that each variable has a high degree of convergent validity, which is the recommended minimum limit. The Burnout variable has an AVE of 0.531, indicating that 53.1% of the indicator's variance can be explained by the construct. Compensation and Job Satisfaction have the same AVE, which is 0.611, meaning that each construct is able to explain 61.1% of the indicator's variance. Meanwhile, the Turnover Intention variable shows the highest level of convergent validity with an AVE of 0.674 (67.4%). Thus, all variables meet the convergent validity criteria, indicating that the indicators in each variable have a fairly strong ability to represent the construct being measured. Because each variable's correlation value is higher than the correlation value of the others, the following table demonstrates the validity of this study assertion.

Table 5. Early Fornell Lacker

Variables	Burnout	Compensation	Turnover Intention	Job Satisfaction
Burnout	0.887			
Compensation	0.878	0.879		
Turnover Intention	0.742	0.728	0.821	
Job Satisfaction	0.852	0.845	0.796	0.878

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The off-diagonal inter-variable correlations are less than the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), suggesting that each variable has strong discriminant validity. Burnout has a high correlation with Compensation (0.878) and Job Satisfaction (0.852), indicating a close relationship between these variables. Turnover Intention has a moderate correlation with Burnout (0.742) and Job Satisfaction (0.796), indicating a significant relationship but not as strong as the other relationships. Overall, these results indicate that the variables in this study have adequate validity and reliability to be used in further analysis.

There are two ways to demonstrate dependability: Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. The table that follows states that a variable is deemed reliable if both its Cronbach's alpha value and composite reliability value are more than 0.6 and 0.7, respectively (Ghozali, 2014).

Table 6. Initial Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha Results

Variables	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
Burnout	0.913	0.911
Compensation	0.910	0.909
Turnover Intention	0.922	0.919
Job Satisfaction	0.943	0.942

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The reliability analysis's findings demonstrate that every variable in the model has extremely high Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values, surpassing the 0.7 threshold and signifying strong internal consistency. With a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.911 and a Composite dependability rating of 0.913, the Burnout variable has very strong dependability. With a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.909 and a Composite Reliability rating of 0.910, compensation exhibits a comparable degree of dependability. With a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.919 and a Composite Reliability rating of 0.922, Turnover Intention is the most reliable of the other factors. On the other hand, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.942 and a Composite Reliability of 0.943, Job Satisfaction exhibits the best overall reliability. This shows that every indicator in the model accurately and consistently depicts the variables it represents.

Structural Model (Inner Model)

To assess the impact of independent variables on dependent variables, endogenous variables are subjected to the determination coefficient test (R^2). It is deemed strong if the R square value is greater than 0.67, moderate if it is greater than 0.33 but less than 0.67, and weak if it is greater than 0.19 but less than 0.33.

Table 7. Determination Coefficient Test

Variables	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Turnover Intention	0.651	0.647
Job Satisfaction	0.767	0.766

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The turnover intention construct's Adjusted R-Square score is 0.647, which shows that the model fits the data well and that 64.7% of the variability in turnover intention can be accounted for by the variables in the model. The work satisfaction construct's Adjusted R-Square score is 0.766, which shows that the model fits the data well and that 64.7% of the variation in job satisfaction can be accounted for by the variables in the model.

Ghozali & Latan (2014:81) state that the PLS model is evaluated using the Q^2 predictive relevance test. The test condition is that the model has predictive significance if Q^2 is greater than 0.

Table 8. Q Square Test

	SSO	SSE	$Q^2 (=1-SSE/SSO)$
Burnout	3333,000	3333,000	0,000
Compensation	2424,000	2424,000	0,000
Turnover Intention	2121,000	1213,639	0.428
Job Satisfaction	3636,000	1951,580	0.463

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The turnover intention variable's Q^2 value is 0.428, indicating a strong influence from the variables influencing turnover intention. In the meantime, the job satisfaction variable Q^2 value is 0.463, indicating that the factors influencing job satisfaction have a considerable impact.

The p value < 0.05 and t statistic ≥ 1.96 can be calculated to assess whether there is a positive or negative influence and whether the results are significant (Ghozali, 2014).

Table 9. Direct Influence Significance Test

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Burnout → Turnover Intention	0.175	3,514	0.013
Burnout → Job Satisfaction	-0.483	-6,998	0,000
Compensation → Turnover Intention	-0.098	-2,997	0.019
Compensation → Job Satisfaction	0.421	6,040	0,000
Job Satisfaction → Turnover Intention	-0.565	-5,996	0,000

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The burnout variable original sample value on the work satisfaction variable was negative, at -0.483, with a t statistic of -6.998 (t statistic > 1.96), and a p value of 0.000, indicating that it had a significant impact. The study's H1 hypothesis is therefore deemed to be acceptable.

The burnout variable has a significant impact on turnover intention, as evidenced by the original sample value of 0.175, a t statistic of 3.514 (t statistic > 1.96), and a p value of 0.013 (p value < 0.05). Thus, the study's H2 hypothesis is disproved.

It can be stated to have a significant impact because the first sample value of the compensation variable on work satisfaction is positive, namely 0.421 with a t statistic of 6.040 (t statistic > 1.96) and a p value of 0.000 (p < 0.05).

The compensation variable original sample value on turnover intention was negative, namely -0.098, with a t statistic of -2.997 (t statistic < 1.96) and a p value of 0.013 (p value < 0.05), indicating a significant effect.

With a t statistic of -5.996 (t statistic > 1.96), a p value of 0.000 (p value < 0.05), and a negative initial sample value of -0.565 for the work satisfaction variable on turnover intention, it can be considered to have a substantial impact.

Table 10. Direct Influence Significance Test

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Burnout → Job Satisfaction → Turnover Intention	-0.273	-4,424	0,000
Compensation → Job Satisfaction → Turnover Intention	-0.238	-4,427	0,000

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The burnout variable's original sample value on turnover intention through the work satisfaction variable is negative, at -0.273, with a t statistic of 4.424 (t statistic > 1.96), and a p value of 0.000 (p value < 0.05), indicating that it has a significant impact. Thus, the H6 hypothesis of this research is approved.

With a t statistic of -4.427 (t statistic > 1.96), a p value of 0.000 (p value < 0.05), and a negative initial sample value of -0.238 for the salary variable on the turnover intention variable through the job satisfaction variable, it may be said to have a substantial impact.

Discussion

The results of this study found a significant positive effect of burnout on job satisfaction with an original sample estimate of -0.483 with a t statistic of -6.998 (t statistic > 1.96) and a p value of 0.000. Ajiputra et al. (2016) conducted a study at PT. Lotus Indah Textile Industries This study found that work stress and fatigue were influenced by employee job satisfaction. Based on existing research and this study, it can be concluded that there is a negative effect of Burnout on job satisfaction. The greater the burnout felt by employees, the more job dissatisfaction they get. The indicator that has the highest value on burnout is personal accomplishment.

By increasing these indicators, especially on salary and supervision, it can increase job satisfaction so that it can also improve hospital services.

The study Charly et al. (2022) findings indicated that burnout had a significant positive impact on turnover intention, with an original sample estimate of 0.175, a t statistic of 3.514 (t statistic > 1.96), and a p value of 0.013 (p value < 0.05). A T-Statistics value of 4.494 and a P Value of 0.000 indicate that burnout significantly increases the turnover intention variable by 44.2%. The turnover intention variable is positively impacted by burnout by 44.2%, with a T-Statistics value of 4.494 and a P Value of 0.000. Burnout has a favorable impact on turnover intention, according to the data that is currently available. If workers are under more stress, they are more likely to quit the company. Decreased operational stability due to high turnover intention can cause many job vacancies, which can disrupt the continuity of health services. In-depth strategies to address job loss and reduce intent to leave are organizational interventions to create a pleasant work environment by reducing work stress, providing recognition for employee contributions, and ensuring fairness in hospital policies. To prevent responsibility from being concentrated on certain individuals, fair distribution of work uses effective workforce management.

With an original sample estimate of 0.421, a t statistic of 6.040 (t statistic > 1.96), and a p value of 0.000 (p < 0.05), the study's findings demonstrated a strong positive impact of salary on job satisfaction. This result supports Satyawati & Suartana's (2014) conclusion that there is a substantial and favorable relationship between employee job satisfaction and compensation. With competitive compensation, employees are motivated to do more and better, increasing job satisfaction and work motivation. If employees feel financially rewarded, they are more likely to do their best in their jobs. Adequate compensation helps them manage their living needs, allowing them to focus on their work without losing money. Special implementation with a unique incentive program rewards employees who help achieve company goals.

The results of this study found a significant negative effect of compensation on Turnover Intention with the original sample estimate of -0.098. Then, the t statistic of 2.997 > 1.96 and p value of 0.000 (p < 0.05) can be seen so that it can be said to have a significant effect. The higher the compensation given to health workers and health support staff, the lower the likelihood they will leave the hospital. Yudhistira (2017) stated that compensation has a significant negative impact on the intention to sell. The turnover intention variable is also negatively affected by the compensation variable (Ajiputra, 2016). Health workers and support staff who perform well can leave the company because of uncompetitive compensation. Due to high turnover, it is necessary to recruit and train new employees, which is time consuming and costly. It is possible that the remaining employees will be tired due to the greater workload. Due to employee turnover, productivity and service quality decline, which often disrupts team stability and patient health services. Employee dissatisfaction shows the impact of turnover on the hospital's high reputation, which can affect the public's and prospective employees' perceptions of the hospital.

With a t statistic of -5.996 (t statistic > 1.96), a p value of 0.000 (p value < 0.05), and an initial sample estimate of -0.565, the study's findings demonstrated a significant negative impact of burnout on job satisfaction. Thus, this study's Hypothesis H5 is deemed to be accepted. Purwanti et al. (2022), which found that job satisfaction has a negative impact on turnover intention, supports this. Mayawati (2021) shows that job satisfaction affects nurse turnover intentions. Fitriantini et al. (2020) found that job satisfaction affects turnover intentions in health workers and health support staff. Employees are dissatisfied with their jobs, they are more likely to look for jobs elsewhere. High turnover rates lead to high turnover, team instability, and low quality of service. Hospitals can experience increased operational costs due to recruitment costs, training new employees, and the time it takes to adjust to new employees. While some employees show a desire to leave, this can negatively impact team morale and productivity, and overall team spirit can decline, which can lead to more employee dissatisfaction.

The results of this study found a significant negative effect of burnout on turnover intention with mediation of job satisfaction, the original sample value was -0.273 with a t statistic of 4.424 (t statistic > 1.96) and a p value of 0.000 (p value < 0.05) so that it can be stated to have a significant effect. Research (Rulianti et al., 2021) fatigue can affect the desire to leave work through decreased job satisfaction. However, it should be noted that the effect of fatigue on the desire to leave work through the mediation of job satisfaction can vary depending on the situation and a number of other factors. According to research by Dewi et al. (2019) that job satisfaction, a mediator variable, significantly mediates the relationship between work stress and employee desire to resign.

With a t statistic of -4.427 (t statistic > 1.96), a p value of 0.000 (p value < 0.05), and a negative original sample value of -0.238 for the compensation variable on the turnover intention variable through the job satisfaction variable, the study's findings indicate that it has a significant impact. According to Saputra (2022), pay has a partial impact on turnover intention. According to Husin & Kadir

(2021), the relationship between organizational climate and turnover intention is mediated by work satisfaction. We can conclude that the relationship between organizational climate and turnover intentions is mediated by job satisfaction. When employees receive low, unclear, or inappropriate compensation for their responsibilities, they feel unappreciated and will leave the company. Increase employee satisfaction through recognition and rewards, a supportive work environment, and opportunities for development. The long-term strategy to reduce turnover intention is to create a work-life balance, employee loyalty programs, transparent communication, and fair recognition, and provide equal opportunities for supporting employees to participate in training and awards. It should be noted that the effect of compensation on turnover intention through the mediation of job satisfaction can vary depending on the situation and other factors.

Research Limitations

This study has several limitations, which can be used as further research development. First, the study was only conducted in one private hospital in Tangerang. Therefore, the results cannot be generalized to medical personnel in other places, government hospitals, or other health facilities. Second, regarding the method of data collection with a questionnaire, it can cause response bias, such as social desirability, where respondents may give answers that are considered "good" by the organization. Our understanding of the causal relationship between variables can be limited if there is no longitudinal data. Third, regarding the characteristics of respondents, the diversity of professions of health workers and health support personnel, such as doctors, nurses, and administrative staff, can affect their views on burnout, compensation, and job satisfaction. Fourth, this study only examines the variables of burnout, compensation, and job satisfaction as predictors of turnover intention. Other factors, such as the work environment, managerial support, organizational culture, and career opportunities, are not examined in this study. Fifth, measuring the variables of fatigue and job satisfaction. The use of subjective scales to measure fatigue, job satisfaction, and turnover expectations can cause perception bias because it depends on the emotional condition of the respondent when answering.

V. CONCLUSION

Conclusion

Burnout has a positive and substantial impact on turnover intention (original sample: 0.175; t statistic: 3.514; p value: 0.013) and a negative and significant impact on work satisfaction (original sample: -0.483; t statistic: -6.998; p value: 0.000), according to the report. Both job satisfaction and turnover intention are significantly impacted by compensation (original sample: 0.421; t statistic: 6.040; p value: 0.000 and -0.098; t statistic: -2.997; p value: 0.013, respectively). Turnover intention is significantly and negatively impacted by job satisfaction (original sample: -0.565; t statistic: -5.996; p value: 0.000). Furthermore, burnout (original sample: -0.273; t statistic: 4.424; p value: 0.000) and compensation (original sample: -0.238; t statistic: -4.427; p value: 0.000) both have a negative and significant impact on turnover intention through the mediation of job satisfaction.

Recommendation

Based on the results of this study and its limitations, the suggestions for further research are first, to increase the generalizability of the results, include more hospitals with various types (government, private, urban, rural). Second, to complete the quantitative data, use mixed methods, such as in-depth interviews. Third, it is necessary to look at other factors such as leadership style, work environment, managerial support, organizational culture, and career opportunities, and work-life balance, also known as work-life balance. Fourth, further research can use research designs such as case control. Fifth, further research can use the same variables with a larger research location, larger sample size, or other research subjects.

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